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Discovery and characterization of O-glycan selective proteins from the human gut microbiota

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Keywords: O-glycan, microbiota, *B. caccae*, *B. thetaiotaomicron*

The mucus layer of intestinal epithelium contains extensively O-glycosylated proteins, mucins. How mucin O-glycans are differentially exploited by the microbiota and influence the crosstalk with the human host largely remains to be elucidated at the molecular level^[1]. Two prominent commensal bacteria, *Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron* and *B. caccae*, show increased activity on mucin O-glycans in conditions of a low-fiber diet and are implicated in susceptibility to infection^[2, 3]. In this communication, we will report the characterization of newly identified proteins (glycan-binding proteins and enzymes) from these bacteria, which are encoded by sets of co-regulated genes termed polysaccharide utilization loci systems (PULs) that target a specific glycan structure^[2]. Through sequence and structural bioinformatic analysis of the bacterial genomes, we selected several putative glycan-binding proteins for high-throughput production and ligand discovery using microarrays of human mucin-type glycoproteins and sequence-defined glycans^[4-6]. Structurally characterization of proteins targeting mucin O-GalNAc-Thr/Ser cores and Tn antigen by X-ray crystallography^[7] led to uncovering their molecular determinants for mucin O-glycan recognition. Associated O-glycan selective catalytic domains with potential biotechnological use are currently under characterization. We expect this study to help understand the role of commensal bacteria in gut health and in designing new therapeutic and diagnostic strategies.

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We acknowledge FCT-MCTES (2022.06104.PTDC, UIDP/04378/2020, UIDB/04378/2020, LA/P/0140/2020); HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417-GLYCOTwinning; COST CA18103 and Wellcome Trust (218304/Z/19/Z).